

Research

Patient Satisfaction Level Assessment at Out Patient Departments of District Level Hospital in Bangladesh

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Abstract: A Cross Sectional study was conducted to understand the level of satisfaction in different categories of variable at selected district level of Hospital named Shaheed Ahsan Ullah Master General Hospital, Tongi Gazipur 1710 ,Dhaka Bangladesh. A Modern Government Hospital in Bangladesh there was total 105 respondent and majority 76 percent of the respondent were female, mean age was 2.0952 years ranging from 0-85 years with the majority of the age group were within 16-30 years. Majority 95percent were Muslims minority representation was 1percent Buddhist religion respectfully. Living status: Majority respondent live in rural 60percent, and minority live in urban 45percent area.

These demographic statistics provide valuable insights into the composition of the study population, which is essential for understanding the context of the research findings and their potential implications.

Results: the various level of satisfaction regarding behavior of health care providers shows that , 60percent are strongly satisfied, with the service of pathology, Pharmacy and Xray department, most of the clients are satisfied with the care they received from the hospital staff. Among the level of satisfaction regarding payment correspondences service & shows that 84 percent are satisfied, & 21 percent are not satisfied, where as total respondent are 105. Only some of the respondent were dissatisfied about the cleanliness of hospital environment of OPD department and outside area.

the various level of satisfaction regarding outdoor service it was observed that 22 percent are strongly satisfied, 16percent only satisfied, 11percent are neutral, 11percent dissatisfied, and 45percent are strongly dissatisfied. Regarding admission procedure shows that, 97percent are satisfied, & only 8 percent are not satisfied out of 105 respondent.

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Likert scale :Each indicator of satisfaction was split into a number of questions and the answer to each question was measured by using five (5) points Likert scale. The answers were ranked in 5 scales as Very satisfied=5,satisfied=4, nor satisfied nor dissatisfied =3, dissatisfied=2 and very dissatisfied=1.

OPD clinics : patients expectations at the ghat , reception and wards: most of the patient had come for a second or subsequent visit, they did not find help at the entrance ghat, or the reception desk .Those who did had the opinion that the people at the gate were helpful more than 50percent patient's rated the assistance given at the reception . Some OPD patients also report that they did not find OPD care in every day.

Keywords: Hospital, OPD, patients satisfaction.

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Introduction

Intergrating the health sector into poverty reduction plan in developing countries like Bangladesh is not just a matter of providing medical care but also a strategic plan towards sustainable socio-economic development. Measuring patient satisfaction is indeed essential the gaps between expected and experienced service , healthcare providers can improve their services and enhance patient outcomes.

Incorporating patients satisfaction measurement into hospital management strategies is a gloval trend. It helps healthcare facilities identify areas for improvement , optimize resource allocation, and ultimately enhance the overall quality of care , in many countries its arequirement for quality assurance processes, ensuring accountability and continuous improvement in healthcare delivery.

Overaall prioritizing patient satisfaction in health sector is not just about meeting regulatory standards, its about fullfilling the fundamental purpose of healthcare: to provide effective compassionate, and patient-centered services that contribute to better health outcomes and socio-economic development.

Although improving hospital performance requires a comprehensive approach that addresses these concern while also considering factors like as clinical outcomes, patient safety, and organizational efficiency. Collaboration between healthcare providers , policymakers and communities is essential to identify areas for improvement and implement strategies to enhance hospital performance. The aims of this study were (i)to determine the socio demographic characteristic of patient.(ii)to compare the level of satisfaction in out patient patients regarding services.(iii)to compare the socio demographic characteristics with the level of satisfaction among patients.

Table-1 The following chart shows the socio-demographic characteristics of patients

Table-2 The following chart shows the distribution of patient showing satisfaction towards each component of service they received from the service provider

Tab- 3 Distribution of patients showing overall satisfaction towards the service, High level of satisfaction indicates > 88 (45percent) and lower level of satisfaction indicates <88 (55percent) respectively

Research Methodology

Methods and Materials:

This was a cross sectional study. It was conducted in Bangladesh. The study was conducted from November 2023 to April 2024. Mainly out door patient were the target population of this study. The study place was selected purposively where a total 105 patients were selected also using purposive sampling technique. Data collection was accomplished by face to face interview with a set of questionnaire and check list also filled in interviewing the right respondents. The data were compiled and analyzed by using SPSS 25, Python 3.12.3 and R-4.4.0 software.

Sample Size: Total patients were 105. According to the statistic formula of sample size, by assuming (P) as 0.5 and degree of accuracy desired setting (d) at 0.065 and z-score of 1.96 at 95percent confidence interval, N is calculated as 228, but due to short duration of time sample size of 105 was arbitrarily chosen. To measured the satisfaction level 5 points liked scale are used.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who are agreed to give willingly interview.
2. Outdoor patient of Hospital.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients who are not agree or not interested to give interview.
2. Patients cannot speak (mute) or listen (deaf).
3. Patients in the serious health condition.
4. Mentally ill patient

Conflict of Interest: there was no conflict of interest among the researcher.

Recommendation: On the basis of the findings of the current study following recommendations has been suggested:

1. A massive awareness could be increases on important of taking care of own health of individuals
2. More Importance could be given on the health seeking behavior especially for the females.

3. A comprehensive treatment plan is to be instituted before the patient is discharged from the hospital to help the patient and his caregiver to understand and follow accurately the required therapeutic regimen
4. 4. Follow up visits either to the hospital or through home visits is important in order to evaluate the progress of patient's condition and motivate them to adhere with preventive measures through promoting healthy lifestyle to prevent complications.
5. Ambulance services should be improvement to transfer the referred patient to other hospital immediately from emergency department.
6. As study areas were selected purposively & the study was conducted only OPD patient, the results may not be generalized overall scenario of patient's satisfaction level in Bangladesh at all.
7. Same study could be conducted with large population to confirm the findings.

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